

FORMS OF GREETING AND ADDRESS IN THE UZBEK AND GERMAN PEOPLES

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Annotation

This article discusses the culture of greetings in the Uzbek and German languages and features of the forms of address.

Key words: Greeting culture, forms of address, formal, informal, norm, intimacy, familiarity, stranger, respect, name.

Nowadays, comparison and study of peoples that are far from each other in culture and traditions is one of the urgent problems.

Below we would like to compare the greeting culture and forms of address of the German and Uzbek people. Moreover, analyzing common and different aspects of the greeting culture and forms of address is planned.

In German people, it is common to say "Guten Morgen" (Good morning), "Guten Tag" (Good afternoon), "Guten Abend" (Good evening) depending on the time of day in official circles. In informal circles, for example, depending on the time of day, older people are welcomed "morgen" (morning), "tag" (afternoon), "abend" (evening). Even saying "hallo" is more preferable among youngsters before, the English version of greeting "Hi" is used commonly these days. It is customary for Uzbeks to greet as "Assalomu alaykum" not only in official, but also in unofficial circles.

The Germans use the handshake almost every day in official circles, but in unofficial circles it is used only when they first meet each other. Uzbeks greet each other with a handshake in official circles, but in unofficial circles, that is, among friends, acquaintances and colleagues, one can sometimes see a handshake, and sometimes hugs.

The Germans have their own custom of greeting men and women standing nearby. For example, formally, when a high-ranking person greets people in other positions, he always greets the first woman, regardless of his position. But if a high-ranking person is younger than the one whom he greets, then out of respect he greets the older, and not the woman.

This situation is slightly different among the Uzbek people. In Muslim countries, men are the first to greet a man, because men are held in high esteem. Greeting in women depends on the situation, sometimes it is greeted with a handshake, and sometimes with a hand on the chest.

Among the Uzbek and German peoples, the clash of sincere glances with each other during a greeting is certainly considered a sign of culture. Talking or looking at the other person while greeting is a bad habit and is considered a sign of disrespect for the person you are greeting.

The Germans have their own greeting rules in official state institutions. While receiving their clients the head of the department and the head of the chair, or while doctors are receiving their patient, it's norm to stand up and shake hands. Failure to stand up and shake hands is considered disrespectful to the client and patient. It is considered a moral norm to hand over

any document that should be given away in such places, or, conversely, to push a document in a seat without taking it is a gross violation of the norm. This situation is slightly different among the Uzbek people. It is not considered normal for a boss or doctor to greet a client or patient by standing up and shaking hands. The visitor enters with the words "Assalomu alaykum" (Good Morning), the head or the doctor greets him only in his place or a little excitedly with phrases like "Vaalaykum assalom, keling, marhamat o'tiring, eshitaman" (Hello, come, please sit down, I will listen).

Forms of address are vital for conducting communication in the necessary way among all peoples: through the appeal, one can single out the social group of the listener, his age, gender, the task he performs, and other factors. Forms of address occupy a special place with their tasks; they determine the social relations of speakers based on their social tasks. It was found that the appeal means not only the meaning of the call and greeting, but sometimes it also serves to express other purposes, based on the situation.

"I beg your pardon. When will the bus come to Ferghana?", "Entschuldigung, wann kann ich das anfangen?" (Excuse me, when can I start this?) - both examples of attracting attention and apologizing are not a form of link, it functions as a form of link, age, gender, social function of the listener are not reflected here, there is no naming / nomination of the listener.

Among the Uzbek people, the use of kinship hyponyms in the process of communicating with unfamiliar listeners differs only on the basis of age and gender. For example, they are addressed as aunt or uncle. The Germans "Entschuldigung..." (sorry...) refer to strangers regardless of age. In both nations, when addressing close family members and dear acquaintances, names are often abbreviated. For example, it is custom for Germans to abbreviate a girl named Katarina as Karin, a girl named Evangelia as Eva, a boy named Stefan as Stefi, and a boy named Rudolf as Rudy. One can understand the meaning of caress by using this shorthand notation. This situation is also typical for the Uzbek people, in which the meaning of closeness and affection of the addressee is hidden. For example, we may find that a girl named Fatima is referred to as Fati, a girl named Gulnoza is referred to as Gulnoz or Guli, a boy named Nuriddin is referred to as Nuri, and a boy named Fakhriddin is referred to as Fahri. Secondary designations of kinship, used in relation to non-relatives, acquire an additional meaning among Uzbeks, in which not only each speech act, but also the corresponding signs used as a linguistic unit, acquire an additional meaning. Such appeals have an evaluative-connotative nature and determine the nuances of interaction between communicators.

Among the German people, there are no secondary designations of kinship at all, which are used in relation to people who are not relatives. It is customary to call a person by his first name, regardless of whether he is older or younger or the same age.

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